

Modelling non-isothermal transport behaviour of real gas in deformable coal matrix

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Abstract

This paper presents a coupled thermo-hydraulic-mechanical (THM) model to study real gas flow behaviour in a deformable coal matrix. The matrix encompasses multiple pore sizes, ranges from nanometers to micrometers, and it promotes various complex, inter-related mass transport mechanisms. In this model, the adsorbed gas layer at the interface between the solid matrix and the free gas phase is considered as an independent phase. Gas adsorption/ desorption and diffusion process are defined separately for individual phases, which are then interacted via mass exchange between the phases. The Knudsen number-based flow regimes are adopted to describe bulk gas transport in the matrix of varying pore sizes, and the adsorbed phase transport is described by surface diffusion mechanisms. The thermal effect on gas adsorption and transport behaviour is investigated. In addition, the mechanical behaviour is included to consider the stress dependency of the porosity and intrinsic permeability of porous rocks. The validity of proposed model is achieved by comparing numerical solutions with published experimental data. Numerical simulations were performed to investigate the real gas transport processes in coal matrix of multiple pore sizes. The simulated results show that the times to reach pressure equilibrium and adsorption equilibrium are not same, and they depend on the pore size, pressure and surface diffusion. Time required to reach equilibrium is reduced significantly with increase of pore sizes. Diffusion coefficients in porous matrix are not constant but vary with pressure and pore sizes, which is important for accurate estimation of coalbed gas production or carbon sequestration.

Keywords: THM model, real gas, adsorption/desorption; gas transport; porous matrix

1 Introduction

Coal has unique characteristics, such as pore structure, gas storage mechanism, flow and transport process that are different from conventional reservoirs. Generally, coalbeds are characterized by natural fracture networks and matrix blocks containing a highly heterogenous porous structure between fractures¹⁻³. Gas transport processes in coalbed methane (CBM) production consists of gas desorption from the internal micropore wall, diffusion from matrix block to fracture system, and then flow to well through fracture networks⁴. For greenhouse gas sequestration, the transport process is reversed. Gas

transport in matrix is the intermediate step of gas transport in coal and it can become a controlling factor in CBM production and CO₂ storage, especially for high permeability reservoirs⁵. A better and comprehensive understanding of the diffusion behaviour of these gases in coal is of great importance for an efficient development of CO₂ sequestration in coal and/or CH₄ extraction from coalbed.

The high complexity of gas transport in coal matrix mainly derives from the extremely intricate and heterogeneous pore structure. It has been demonstrated that the pore size distribution is dependent on coal organic matter composition and thermal maturity^{6,7}. Coal matrix has a variety of pore sizes, ranging from a few nanometers to over a micrometer^{8,9}. Pore gas, generally, not only flow within the micropores but also can be adsorbed onto the surface of micropores, leading to unusual transport behaviours^{5,10}. In a typical unconventional reservoir, such as coalbeds, multiple gas transport mechanisms including viscous flow, free molecular diffusion (Knudsen diffusion), surface diffusion, and continuum diffusion may coexist due to pore pressure, temperature variations, and the pore size distribution in the low permeability matrix^{11,12}. Therefore, it is of significant interest to investigate the gas transport behaviour in multiscale coal structure together with adsorption process.

Over the past decades, various transport models have been developed to investigate the transport behaviour of gases in porous media. For example, Ertekin, et al.¹³ adopted a dual mechanism approach of gas flow in tight formations by combining viscous flow process with Darcy's law and Knudsen flow process with Fick's law. In general, the Knudsen number (K_n) is used to classify the different flow regimes of bulk gas transport¹⁴: viscous flow ($K_n < 0.001$), Knudsen diffusion ($K_n > 10$), slip flow ($0.001 < K_n < 0.1$) and transition flow ($0.1 < K_n < 10$). Based on this classification, Beskok and Karniadakis¹⁵ derived a unified Hagen–Poiseuille-type equation for predicting mass flow rate and pressure distribution through a single pipe, which was then improved by Civan¹⁶ for a bundle of tortuous capillary tubes and represented the effects of characteristic parameters such as intrinsic permeability, porosity, and tortuosity. Fathi and Akkutlu^{17,18} presented a theoretical model to investigate diffusive transport and adsorption of ideal gases in heterogenous porous media such as coal and shale matrices. The classic small perturbation theory is employed to consider the influence of local spatial heterogeneities on gas transport process in presence of non-equilibrium adsorption. Particularly, the Péclet number is used to measure the contribution of viscous flow and diffusion to the macro-scale transport of ideal gases in those matrices. Wu et al.^{19,20} presented analytical models to study transport of real gases in nanopores of shale reservoirs. The complex, multiple pore size distribution of the matrix and the associated transport were described using the Knudsen number. They emphasised on the adsorbed state transport i.e. surface diffusion of gases in the shale matrix and they reported that transport of real gases in nanopores can be significantly influenced by surface diffusion processes. The previous models, however, do not consider the effects of important coupled subsurface conditions, e.g. thermal gradient, overburden pressure or changes in the stress field. Gas adsorption in porous media is generally affected by a number of factors, such as temperature, pressure and stress conditions²¹⁻²³. Mathematical

models that study these complex and coupled interactions on the transport of real gases in tight porous materials are rarely available.

The purpose of this work is to develop a non-isothermal transport model for real gases in deformable coal matrix highlighting the gas diffusion/adsorption behaviour. The adsorbed gas at the interface between solid and free gas phase is viewed as an independent phase and it obeys the mass conservation laws. The adsorption/desorption processes and the bulk gas flow process are not lumped together, but considered separately based on different transport mechanisms, as shown in Fig.1. In addition, the gas transport is coupled with matrix deformation and thermal behaviour. The model considers changes in stress-dependent porosity, permeability, and temperature effect on gas transport and adsorption behaviour. The flow regimes in multipore coal matrix are described using the Knudsen number, and the transport of bulk gas phase and adsorbed gas phase is integrated in a coupled thermo-hydraulic-mechanical (THM) modelling framework. The structure of current work is organized as follows: firstly, four governing equations e.g. thermo-poroelastic mechanical deformation, free and adsorbed gas phase transport, and heat transfer are presented; and then the model is validated by comparing with published experimental data. Following that, the developed model is applied to investigate the real gas transport behaviours in coal matrices.

Fig. 1 Gas transport process in pore structure: (a) physical illustration and (b) model representation.

2 Model development

In this section, a set of governing equations for describing gas transport in deformable porous media under non-isothermal conditions is presented. The details of the coupled THM model including multi-component gas and chemical transport are available in Thomas and He²⁴, Masum and Thomas²⁵, Chen et al.³, Hosking, et al.²⁶. Here, the theoretical framework is extended to include the nanopore gas transport processes. The coupled model consists of four main components: the thermo-poroelastic mechanical model, free and adsorbed gas phase transport models, and heat transfer model under local thermal non-equilibrium. The three primary flow variables are, namely, the bulk gas concentrations (C), adsorbed gas concentration (C_s), and temperature (T). The displacement vector (\mathbf{u}) is the primary

variable for mechanical deformation model. This paper is focused on gas transport in dry coal matrices, and therefore the hydraulic behaviour is neglected.

2.1 Thermo-poroelastic mechanical model

It is assumed that the rock matrix is homogenous, isotropic, and the deformation is linearly elastic. As per the traditional conventions, a comma followed by subscripts denotes the differential with respect to the spatial coordinates and the repeated indices denote a summation over the range of the indices. Here, stress and strain are positive in tension, whereas fluid pressure is positive for compression. Stress equilibrium is expressed as ²⁷:

$$\sigma_{ij,j} + F_j = 0 \quad (1)$$

where σ_{ij} is the component of the total stress tensor and F_i is the component of the body force vector.

The total stress can be expressed in terms of the effective stress and the average pore pressure according to Biot's effective stress law ²⁷ as:

$$\sigma'_{ij} = \sigma_{ij} - \alpha p \delta_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where σ'_{ij} is the component of the effective stress tensor, p is pore fluid pressure, δ_{ij} is Kronecker's delta tensor ($\delta = 1$ for $i = j$, $\delta_{ij} = 0$ for $i \neq j$), α is Biot's coefficient and it is given by ²⁷:

$$\alpha = 1 - \frac{K}{K_s} \quad (3)$$

where $K = E/3(1 - 2\nu)$ is the bulk modulus of the rock matrix with E being Young's modulus, K_s is the modulus of the solid constituent, and ν is Poisson's ratio.

The stress-strain constitutive relationship is ²⁶:

$$\sigma'_{ij} = 2G\varepsilon_{ij}^e + \lambda\varepsilon_v^e \delta_{ij} \quad (4)$$

where $G = E_e/2(1 + \nu)$ is the shear modulus, $\lambda = E_e\nu/(1 + \nu)(1 - 2\nu)$ is the Lamé constant, E_e is Young's modulus, ε_{ij}^e represents the component of the elastic strains, and $\varepsilon_v^e = \varepsilon_{11}^e + \varepsilon_{22}^e + \varepsilon_{33}^e$ is the elastic volumetric strain.

The total strain, ε_{ij} , can be expressed as ²⁶:

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \varepsilon_{ij}^e + \frac{1}{3}\varepsilon_T\delta_{ij} + \frac{1}{3}\varepsilon_{ad}\delta_{ij} \quad (5)$$

where ε_T is the thermal expansion-induced volumetric strain and ε_{ad} is the adsorption-induced swelling strain.

The strain-displacement relation is ²⁷:

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}) \quad (6)$$

where u_i is the component of the solid displacement vector.

The thermal expansion-contraction strain is defined as:

$$\varepsilon_T = \alpha_T(T - T_0) \quad (7)$$

where α_T is the thermal expansion coefficient and T_0 is the reference temperature.

From experimental data it is evident that volumetric strain associated with gas adsorption is approximately linearly proportional to the amount of adsorbed gas ^{28, 29}, the volumetric strain induced by adsorption is thus approximated as:

$$\varepsilon_{ad} = LC_s \quad (8)$$

where L is the volumetric strain coefficient of the gas, C_s is the adsorbed phase concentration.

It has been recognized that rock permeability and porosity, especially on low-permeability sedimentary rock, are significantly sensitive to the change of effective stress. The exponential relationship is generally applied to describe the permeability changes with effective stress ^{30, 31}, it takes the following form:

$$k = k_0 \exp[-\gamma(\sigma - \sigma_0)] \quad (9)$$

where k denotes the permeability under the effective stress σ , k_0 is the permeability under the effective stress σ_0 at reference state, γ is the stress sensitivity coefficient.

It is generally considered that the relationship between permeability and porosity of a rock undergoing mechanical compaction could be expressed by a power law ³¹, and it is given as:

$$\frac{n}{n_0} = \left(\frac{k}{k_0}\right)^{1/m} \quad (10)$$

where n_0 is porosity at reference stress state, and m is a material constant named the porosity sensitivity exponent.

2.2 Bulk phase gas transport

The mass balance equation for bulk gas transport process is expressed as::

$$\frac{\partial(n_e C)}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot J_f - S \quad (11)$$

Where C is the concentration of the free phase gas, n_e is the effective porosity, J_f is the total flux of gas in bulk phase and S is the sink/source term.

For a single individual gas species, Knudsen diffusion and viscous flow are two kinds of transport models that could make simultaneous contributions to bulk phase gas transport within a coal matrix under certain pressure and temperature conditions. In order to characterize the contribution of different transport mechanism to the total gas transport, Wu et al.¹⁹ sets the ratios of the frequency of collisions between the gas molecules and the wall-gas molecules collision frequency to the total collision frequency as the weighting factors of viscous flow and Knudsen diffusion, respectively. Therefore, the total flux of free phase gas can be expressed as a sum of the contributions from viscous flow and Knudsen diffusion¹⁹:

$$J_f = \omega_v J_{fv} + \omega_K J_{fK} \quad (12)$$

where J_{fv} is the gas flux from viscous flow and J_{fK} is the gas flux from Knudsen diffusion. ω_v and ω_K are weighting coefficients for viscous flow and Knudsen flow, respectively.

The gas flux due to viscous flow can be expressed as¹¹:

$$J_{fv} = -\frac{k}{\mu} C \nabla p \quad (15)$$

where k is the permeability of coal matrix. μ is the gas viscosity³² (see Appendix A).

Considering the real gas effect, pressure is expressed as³³:

$$p = ZRTC \quad (16)$$

where R is the universal gas constant, T is temperature, Z is the gas compressibility factor, which is calculated with equation of state proposed by Peng and Robinson³⁴, given in Appendix B.

To describe gas transport in the regime $K_n < 0.1$, Civan¹⁶ presented a gas transport model by idealizing transport in a bundle of tortuous capillary tubes. Based on the assumption of tortuous capillary tubes with the same diameters in porous media, the permeability is given as:

$$k = \frac{n_e r_e^2}{\tau} f(K_n) \quad (17)$$

$$f(K_n) = (1 + \alpha' K_n) \left(1 + \frac{4K_n}{1 - bK_n} \right) \quad (18)$$

where r_e is the effective pore radius, τ is tortuosity, b is slip coefficient (here $b = -1$), α' is the rarefaction coefficient. The dimensionless rarefaction coefficient is correlated empirically by Civan¹⁶:

$$\alpha' = 1.358 \left(1 + \frac{0.178}{K_n^{0.4348}} \right)^{-1} \quad (19)$$

Knudsen number (K_n) is defined as the ratio of a molecular mean free path to the average pore diameter³⁵:

$$K_n = \frac{\lambda}{2r_e} \quad (20)$$

where λ is the mean free path of molecules and r_e is the effective radius of pore size reduced by the diameter of gas molecules adsorbed on the surface.

The mean free path of molecules for a real gas can be expressed as³⁶

$$\lambda = \frac{\mu}{p} \sqrt{\frac{\pi ZRT}{2M}} \quad (21)$$

where M is the gas molar weight.

When the size of gas molecules is comparable to the pore size, its effect on the gas migration cannot be neglected. It is assumed that adsorbent surface is energetically homogenous for adsorption, and only monolayer adsorption onto an adsorbent surface occurs. Thus the gas adsorption behaviour obeys the Langmuir adsorption isotherm, where the adsorbed gas molecules create a single adsorbed layer covering the pore wall surface and reducing the pore radius, as shown in Fig. 2. Xiong, et al.³⁷ presented a Langmuir type relationship to correlate the effective radius of a pore to gas adsorbed layer:

$$r_e = r_h - r_{ad} \quad (22)$$

where r_h is hydraulic radius of the pore and r_{ad} is the equivalent radius occupied by the adsorbed gas molecules, which can be expressed as:

$$r_{ad} = d_m \theta \quad (23)$$

where d_m is the molecular diameter of gas adsorbed on the pore wall, θ is the gas coverage on the wall of micropores. Following the Langmuir adsorption, it can be written as³⁸:

$$\theta = \frac{C_s}{C_L} \quad (24)$$

where C_s is the adsorbed phase concentration and C_L is the maximum adsorbed phase concentration.

When considering the effect of adsorption layer, the effective porosity is defined as follow^{37,38}:

$$n_e = n \left(\frac{r_e}{r_h} \right)^2 \quad (25)$$

where n is the porosity when the adsorption coverage is zero.

Fig. 2 Schematic illustration of change in radius the pores due to gas adsorption.

Combination of equations (17)-(25) and application of real gas law allows equation (15) to be expressed in terms of gas concentration and temperature under non-isothermal conditions, giving:

$$J_{fv} = -D_v \nabla C - D_T \nabla T \quad (27)$$

where

$$D_v = \left(\frac{r_e}{r_h}\right)^4 \frac{k_\infty}{\mu} p(1 + \alpha K_n) \left(1 + \frac{4K_n}{1 - bK_n}\right) \left(1 + \frac{C}{Z} \frac{dZ}{dC}\right) \quad (28)$$

$$D_T = \left(\frac{r_e}{r_h}\right)^4 \frac{k_\infty}{\mu} p(1 + \alpha K_n) \left(1 + \frac{4K_n}{1 - bK_n}\right) \left(\frac{C}{T} + \frac{C}{Z} \frac{\partial Z}{\partial T}\right) \quad (29)$$

where D_v is defined as viscous flow-induced diffusivity (for easy comparison of viscous flow with that Knudsen diffusion below), $k_\infty = \frac{n r_h^2}{\tau 8}$ represents the intrinsic permeability of porous media.

The gas flux caused by Knudsen diffusion is generally defined using Fick's law, expressed as:

$$J_{fK} = -D_K \nabla C \quad (30)$$

where D_K is the Knudsen diffusion coefficient. Darabi, et al.³⁹ presented Knudsen diffusion model as:

$$D_K = \frac{2r_e}{3} \frac{n_e}{\tau} \left(\frac{d_m}{2r_e}\right)^{d_f-2} \sqrt{\frac{8ZRT}{\pi M}} \quad (31)$$

where d_f is the fractal dimension of the pore surface used to consider the effect of pore-surface roughness on the Knudsen diffusion coefficient, which varies between 2 and 3, representing a smooth surface and a space-filling surface, respectively³⁹.

Two weighting factors for viscous flow and Knudsen diffusion are defined as¹⁹:

$$\omega_v = \frac{1}{1 + K_n} \quad (32)$$

$$\omega_K = \frac{1}{1 + 1/K_n} \quad (33)$$

Inserting equation (35-37) into equation (10) produces the total flux:

$$J_f = D_{eff} \nabla C \quad (39)$$

where D_{eff} is defined as the apparent diffusion coefficient⁴⁰, which can be viewed as a sum of effective viscous flow ($\omega_v D_v$) and effective Knudsen diffusivity ($\omega_K D_K$) in this study, i.e.:

$$D_a = \omega_v D_v + \omega_K D_K \quad (40)$$

2.3 Adsorbed phase gas transport

It is assumed that adsorbed gas transport process obeys Fick's law³⁷. The governing transport equation of adsorbed gas can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial[(1 - n_e)C_s]}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot J_s + S \quad (41)$$

where J_s is the surface diffusion flux.

Surface diffusion occurs where molecules are adsorbed to the surface of the porous medium and move along that surface which plays a key role in transport of the adsorbates into the particle. The driving force for surface diffusion is the adsorbed gas concentration gradient^{11, 19}. The quantitative model applied to surface flux follows Fick's law, in which the adsorbed gas is considered as migration of adsorbed molecules on the surface under the macroscopic gradient of the surface concentration, and it is expressed as³⁷:

$$J_s = -(1 - n_e)D_s \nabla C_s \quad (42)$$

in which D_s is the surface diffusion coefficient.

The surface diffusivity may strongly depend on surface concentration and temperature as well as on the interaction between the adsorbate and the solid surface and the structure of the solid surface⁴¹. The concentration gradient is dominant driving force over temperature in case of surface diffusion, therefore, the influence of temperature variation on surface diffusion is neglected here. Chen and Yang⁴² proposed the following famous kinetic method to capture the concentration dependency of the surface diffusivity:

$$D_s = D_s^0 \frac{1 - \theta + \frac{w}{2}\theta(1 - \theta) + (1 - w)\frac{w}{2}\theta^2 H(1 - w)}{\left(1 - \theta + \frac{w}{2}\theta\right)^2} \quad (43)$$

$$H(1 - w) = \begin{cases} 0 & w \geq 1 \\ 1 & 0 \leq w \leq 1 \end{cases} \quad (44)$$

where D_s^0 is the surface diffusivity at zero coverage, which is a function of temperature and gas activation energy, $H(1 - w)$ is the Heaviside function, w is a measure of the degree of blockage by another adsorbed molecule, defined as the ratio of rate constant for blockage to the rate constant for forward migration:

$$w = \frac{w_b}{w_m} \quad (45)$$

where w_b is the constant rate for blockage of surface gas molecule, w_m is the constant rate for forward migration of surface gas molecule. When $w_m > w_b$, i.e. $w < 1$, surface diffusion occurs no matter the forward position is empty. When $w_m < w_b$, i.e. $w > 1$, gas molecules are blocked and surface diffusion stops. Chen and Yang's Model for non-zero w can yield many patterns for the surface diffusivity variation with loading. For surface diffusion where there is no effective blockage, i.e. $w = 0$ surface diffusivity reduces to that of the classic HIO theory or Darken theory.

2.4 Heat transfer

The governing equation of heat transfer can be obtained with an energy balance ²⁶:

$$(\rho C_p)_e \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = -J_h + S_h \quad (46)$$

$$(\rho C_p)_e = (1 - n_e)(\rho_s C_{ps} + \rho_a C_{pa}) + n_e \rho_g C_{pg} \quad (47)$$

where C_{pg} , C_{ps} and C_{pa} are the specific heat capacity of free gas, solid skeleton and adsorbed gas, respectively. ρ_g , ρ_s and ρ_a is the density of free gas, solid skeleton and adsorbed gas. Due to limited information on C_{pa} and λ_a for gas adsorption in coal, it is assumed that they are equivalent to C_{pg} and λ_g . S_h is the source term.

Due to slow flow in the porous matrix, pore gas and solid skeleton are always assumed to be in local thermal equilibrium, and therefore ignoring the heat convection, the heat flux can be written as:

$$J_h = -\lambda_e \nabla T \quad (48)$$

where J_h is the heat flux through the rock matrix, λ_e is the effective thermal conductivity of media, which is approximated as ⁴³:

$$\lambda_e = (1 - n_e)(\lambda_s + \lambda_a) + n_e \lambda_g \quad (49)$$

where λ_g and λ_a are the thermal conductivity of free gas and adsorbed gas, respectively, λ_s is the thermal conductivity of solid skeleton.

Considering the real gas effect, the specific heat capacities of the gas phase is calculated with the following thermodynamic relation ³³:

$$C_{pg} = DC_{pg} + C_{pg0} \quad (50)$$

where DC_{pg} is the departure function of specific heat capacity, which is defined as the difference between the specific heat capacity for an ideal gas, C_{pg0} , and that in real case for any temperature and pressure. In this work, PR-EoS is applied to calculate the departure function of specific heat capacity.

The ideal gas specific heat capacity is calculated using a polynomial function with the coefficients presented in Poling, Prausnitz and O'connell³³.

The gas adsorption in coal is not an isothermal process⁴⁴, in this work, the heat supply due to the gas adsorption/desorption induced temperature is considered as the heat source, and it is expressed as⁴⁵:

$$S_h = E \frac{\partial C_s}{\partial t} \quad (51)$$

where E is adsorption heat generated by interaction between the adsorbate and the adsorbent.

2.5 Mass exchange between two phases

Langmuir isotherm, based on the concept of monolayer adsorption, has been extensively considered for gas adsorption in coal matrix, which suggests that there is a kinetic process between adsorbed and free gas phase. The molecule in gas phase striking the surface can be trapped and stay there for a certain amount of time by the surface force (referred to as adsorption). While the adsorbed molecules can move and enter again into gas phase (referred to as desorption)^{46,47}, Fig. 3 shows the dynamic process of gas adsorption onto and desorption from a pore surface of coal matrix. It is usually assumed that single-component sorption behaviour can be described by the so-called Langmuir kinetics, which is nonlinear sorption kinetics behaviour of gas adsorption^{17, 48, 49}. The processes of gas adsorption on internal surfaces and desorption from internal surfaces of the porous structure can therefore be treated as the finite mass exchange between the bulk phase and adsorbed phase macroscopically. The change in amount of adsorbed gas due to phase change is given as^{48, 49}:

$$S = (1 - n_e)(R_a - R_d) \quad (52)$$

where C_s is the adsorbed phase concentration, R_a and R_d are the rates of adsorption and desorption.

Fig. 3 Dynamic adsorption-desorption process of gas molecules on a pore surface of coal matrix.

Langmuir isotherm assumes that the rate of adsorption, R_a , is proportional to the pressure in the gas phase and to the area of free sites and the rate of desorption, R_d , is proportional to the area occupied⁴⁷, expressed as

$$R_a = \gamma_a p(C_L - C_s) \quad (53)$$

$$R_d = \gamma_d C_s \quad (54)$$

where γ_a and γ_d are the rate constant for adsorption and desorption, respectively.

Substitution of equation (53) and (54) into equation (52) and rearrangement lead to the nonequilibrium interchange between the adsorbed and free phase:

$$S = (1 - n_e)\gamma_d[B_L p(C_L - C_s) - C_s] \quad (55)$$

where $B_L = \gamma_a/\gamma_d$ and is generally referred as the reciprocal of Langmuir pressure constant, p_L .

Do and Wang⁴⁹ reported that the rate constant for adsorption is independent of interaction energy but controlled by the rate of collision of molecules to walls of micropores, while rate constant for desorption is a function of adsorption energy, E , between the two phases and obeys the Arrhenius law:

$$\gamma_d = \gamma_{d\infty} \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) \quad (56)$$

where $\gamma_{d\infty}$ is the rate constant of desorption at infinite temperature.

Thus, the effect of temperature on the reciprocal Langmuir pressure can derived as:

$$B_L = B_{L\infty} \exp\left(\frac{E}{RT}\right) \quad (57)$$

where $B_{L\infty}$ is defined as the affinity at infinite temperature. Because of the difficulty for reaching the infinite temperature, B_{L0} at reference temperature can be used to replace $B_{L\infty}$, i.e.:

$$B_L = B_{L0} \exp\left[\frac{E}{R}\left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0}\right)\right] \quad (58)$$

The classic Langmuir model assumed the parameter C_L to be temperature independent, however, the experimental measurements show that C_L decreases with increasing temperature. An exponential relationship between C_L and temperature is usually used to describe the variation of maximum adsorption capacity for the adsorbent^{49,50}, given as:

$$C_L = C_{L0} \exp[-\tau_r(T - T_0)] \quad (59)$$

where C_{L0} is the maximum adsorption capacity of gas at a reference temperature T_0 , and τ_r is a reduction coefficient related with temperature increase.

Equation (55) is known as nonlinear gas sorption kinetics. For subsequent mass conversation equation of bulk phase and adsorbed phase, equation (55) can also be used to represent the mass transfer rate between free and adsorbed phase. It can be seen from equation (54) that when the adsorption reaches equilibrium, equation (55) reduces to the well-known Langmuir isotherm:

$$C_s = C_L(T) \frac{B_L(T)p}{B_L(T)p + 1} = \frac{C_L(T)p}{p + p_L(T)} \quad (60)$$

From equation (55), the phase exchange can be described as follow: initially it is assumed that an equilibrium state occurs between free phase and adsorbed phase, if the free phase gas concentration is increased, the gas pressure will rise, overriding the required pressure for holding current adsorbed gas concentration. If the first term in square bracket is larger than the second term, more free gas will be adsorbed and become adsorbed phase gas. When the adsorbed gas concentration drops, same phenomenon can be envisioned. However, if the free gas concentration decreases, the pressure is insufficient for keeping current gas adsorption equilibrium, the adsorbed gas will desorb and become into the free phase.

Combination of equations (6), (42) and (46) provides a straightforward mathematical model to capture dynamic gas adsorption/desorption-diffusion process in porous media. The governing equations are complex, nonlinear second-order partial different equations that are difficult to solve analytically. In this work, the developed model is implemented into the existing numerical model, COMPASS (CODE of Modelling PARTially Saturated Soils), developed at the Geoenvironmental Research Centre by Thomas and co-workers^{24, 25, 51}. The numerical solution of the governing equations is achieved by applying the finite element method with Galerkin weighted residuals for spatial discretisation and an implicit mid-interval backward-difference scheme for temporal discretisation. The reliability of developed mode for description of gas diffusion behaviour in porous matrix is examined in the subsequent section.

3 Model Validation

Due to lack of comprehensive experimental data/ measurements, three subsets of the developed model are validated here in order to assess the ability and accuracy of the model to predict gas transport behaviour in a multiporous coal matrix.

3.1 Diffusion coefficients prediction for bulk and adsorbed gases

The experimental results published by Dong, et al.⁵² are utilized here. Dong, et al.⁵² applied the counter diffusion method to measure the methane diffusion coefficient of anthracite. They measured the gaseous diffusion coefficient of methane and the surface diffusion coefficient at temperature of 303 K. Thus, the bulk gas diffusion model and the surface diffusion model can be validated separately, suggesting an indirect validation of the comprehensive diffusion model. The parameters used in the validation process are listed in Table 1. Some of the parameters are selected from Dong et al.⁵² and Zhang et al.⁴³, and the others are obtained by fitting experiment data. The porosity-tortuosity factor has a low value compared to general porous media, this is because the pore radius is smaller, and the pore connectivity is weak. The estimated average pore radius is closed to the value obtained from the low pressure methane gas data of Dong et al.⁵². The fitting ratio of rate constants for blockage to forward migration is lower than one, implying that the surface diffusion occurs. It can be seen from Fig. 4 and 5 that the

matching results are appropriate for the proposed model and the proposed gas transport model adequately describe gas transport mechanism in a coal matrix.

Table 1 Parameters used in the proposed model for validation

Parameters	Value	Unit	Source
Temperature, T	303	K	Dong et al. ⁵²
Universal gas constant, R	8.314	J/(mol·K)	Given
Porosity-tortuosity factor, n/τ	1.25e-4	-	Fitting
Gas molar mass, M	0.016	kg/mol	Given
Langmuir pressure constant, u_L	1.13	MPa	Dong et al. ⁵²
Molecular diameter of gas, d_m	0.38	nm	Given
Hydraulic pore radius, r_h	0.63	nm	Fitting
Fractal dimension of the pore surface, d_f	2.0	-	Zhang et al. ⁴³
Surface diffusivity, D_s^0	2.0e-11	m ² /s	Dong et al. ⁵²
Ratio of rate constant, w	0.18	-	Fitting

Fig. 4 Comparison of bulk diffusion coefficient between the proposed model and experimental data.

Fig. 5 Comparison between proposed surface diffusion model and experimental data.

3.2 Impact of temperature on gas adsorption behaviour

Temperature influences the gas adsorption characteristics of coal. Here, the ability of the proposed model to predict the impact of temperature on gas adsorption behaviour is examined. Experimental data from Deng et al.⁵³ is used as a benchmark for this test. Deng et al.⁵³ carried out a number of adsorption experiments to investigate adsorption characteristics of methane on anthracite coal at three temperatures (298 K, 308 K, and 318 K).

The material properties required for the validation exercise were obtained through matching experimental data. The reference temperature T_0 is 298 K. The key parameters used to match the experimental data are: adsorption capacity C_{L0} and Langmuir pressure constant B_{L0} at reference temperature are 1.22 mmol/g and 2.3 MPa^{-1} respectively, which are closed to values obtained by Deng et al.⁵³ using Toth model. The estimated adsorption heat E is 23.1 kJ/mol, which fall within the range 22.49 – 27.92 kJ/mol measured by Deng et al.⁵³. The estimated adsorption capacity reduction coefficient τ_r is 0.002 K^{-1} . The validation result is presented in Fig. 6. It is noticeable that temperature negatively impacts gas adsorption in coal because gas adsorption is an exothermic process. Fig. 6 shows a good agreement between the simulated results and the results of Deng et al.⁵³, which therefore indicates the reliability and the accuracy of the developed model to study temperature dependent gas adsorption behaviours in a coal matrix.

Fig. 6 Comparison between model prediction of gas adsorption and experimental data by Deng et al.⁵³.

3.3 Prediction of gas transport process in coal particles

As described in the introduction, the gas migration in porous matrix is a dynamic process of CBM recovery. It is therefore necessary to examine the performance of the proposed model to interpret the dynamic adsorption/desorption-diffusion processes in a coal matrix. Liu et al.¹⁰ performed a set of experiments on isothermal methane adsorption/desorption-diffusion behaviour in bituminous/sub-bituminous coal at pressures of 1 MPa, 2 MPa and 4 MPa. The coal samples were firstly pulverized and sieved to the desirable particle sizes and then they were dried in oven. The gas desorption test was carried out under different pressure boundary conditions, including constant and variable pressure boundary condition. In this validation exercise, the experiment results of four different size coal particles (YC1, YC2, YC3, YC4) obtained under constant pressure boundary (atmospheric pressure) condition were selected as benchmark. The selected particle sizes and initial pressures, investigated in the experimental measurements, are summarized in Table 2. These values are used in the model simulations.

Table 2 Selected particle sizes and initial pressures in validation test

Number	Particle size range (μm)	Average particle size (μm)	Initial pressure (MPa)
YC1	4000 - 4750	4359	1, 2
YC2	1000 - 1180	1090	2, 4
YC3	425 - 550	487.5	1, 2
YC4	250 - 270	260	2, 4

In the simulations, coal particles are assumed to be spherical with different radii, and the initial pressure is uniform within the particles at the values shown in Table 2. A constant pressure of 0.1 MPa is assigned to the surface of coal particle during the simulation. This fixed gas pressure boundary is converted into the equivalent gas concentrations using the real gas law. Methane adsorption behaviour in coal matrix follows Langmuir isotherm. Table 3 lists the parameters used for this validation exercise. Some of the parameter values are chosen from Liu et al.¹⁰, while the others are obtained by fitting the experimental

results due to lack of relevant information. The estimated surface diffusivity ranges from 0.3×10^{-11} to 3.0×10^{-11} m²/s, which is in the same order of magnitude as the measured values of Dong et al.⁵². The rate constant of desorption, for different particle sizes ranges from 0.6×10^{-5} to 1.0×10^{-5} s⁻¹. This is similar to the values of methane adsorption in shale (0.96×10^{-5} s⁻¹) published by Zhang et al.⁴⁸. The ratio of cumulative amount of methane released from the test samples to the total amount of methane in coal samples is applied to show the comparison between simulated and experimental results, as shown in Fig. 7.

Table 3 Parameters used in the proposed model for validation test

Parameters	Value	Unit	Source
Temperature, T	303	K	Liu et al. ¹⁰
Universal gas constant, R	8.314	J/(mol·K)	Given
Porosity-tortuosity factor, n/τ	1.0e-4	-	Fitting
Gas molar mass, M	0.016	kg/mol	Given
Langmuir pressure constant, u_L	3.33	MPa	Liu et al. ¹⁰
Langmuir constant, C_L	1451	mole/m ³	Liu et al. ¹⁰
Molecular diameter of gas, d_m	0.38	nm	Given
Hydraulic pore radius, r_h	4.38	nm	Fitting
Fractal dimension of the pore surface, d_f	2.0	-	Zhang et al. ⁴³
Surface diffusivity, D_s^0	$(0.3-3.0) \times 10^{-11}$	m ² /s	Fitting
Rate constant of desorption, γ_d	$(0.6-1.0) \times 10^{-5}$	s ⁻¹	Fitting
Solid density, ρ	1250	kg/m ³	Liu et al. ¹⁰

It can be seen from Fig. 7 that the gas desorption-diffusion characteristics predicted by the model achieved an acceptable agreement with the observations of experimental measurements on multiscale coal particles, which is indicative of the reliability and effectiveness of the model. These validation tests presented in this section can lead to the conclusion that the proposed numerical model is able to account for the dynamic desorption-diffusion process affected by various mechanisms of gas transport in a microporous matrix.

Fig. 7 Comparison of residual mass fraction between numerical results and experimental data (solid line: numerical solutions; symbols: experimental data; Q_t : accumulative amount of released methane; Q_0 : total amount of methane).

4 Numerical simulation and discussions

This section presents a model application example. The developed model is applied to investigate the gas transport behaviour in coal matrix of multiple pore sizes, which is achieved by performing a set of numerical simulations. The stress effects will be considered in our future work but not in this study. The coal matrix is considered to be a 1 cm by 1 cm square domain in all numerical simulation scenarios. The model domain is discretized with equally-sized quadrilateral elements, as shown in Fig. 8. Two measuring points, P1 (0.2 cm, 0.2 cm) and P2 (0.5 cm, 0.5 cm) are set to monitor the variations of the gas pressures and adsorbed concentration. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is selected as the flowing gas, the critical point of CO₂ is 304.13 K and 7.38 MPa. The stored CO₂ easily reaches supercritical state during CO₂ geological sequestration. It is assumed that initial pressure is 0.1MPa in the study domain. The state of CO₂ is controlled using different pressures of 6 MPa, 10 MPa and 15 MPa, which are assigned at four sides of domain as boundary condition. The gas temperature of 308 K is used as temperature boundary. In order to understand the effects of nano-scale pore size, different pore sizes of 1, 5, 10, 25 and 50 nm are considered (permeability ranging from 1.5e-23 – 3.9e-20 m²). The parameters used for the numerical simulation is listed in table 4, which are chosen from validation tests above and work by Chen et al.²⁶.

Fig. 8 Discretized model domain and the locations of the observation points.

Table 4 Parameters used in the sensitivity analysis

Parameters	Value	Unit
Temperature, T	308	K
Universal gas constant, R	8.314	J/(mol·K)
Slip coefficient, b	-1	-
Porosity-tortuosity factor, n/τ	1.25e-4	-
Gas molar mass, M	0.044	kg/mol
Langmuir pressure constant, u_L	1.13	MPa
Langmuir volume constant, C_L	1.56	mol/kg
Solid density, ρ	1250	kg/m ³

Molecular diameter of gas, d_m	0.33	nm
Hydraulic radius, r_h	1,5,10,20,50	nm
Fractal dimension of the pore surface, d_f	2.0	-
Ratio of rate constant, w	0.18	-
Surface diffusion, D_s^0	2.0e-10	m ² /s
Rate constant of desorption, γ_d	5×10^{-5}	s ⁻¹
Adsorption heat, E	20.56	kJ/mol
Thermal conductivity of solid, λ_s	0.33	W/m/K
Specific heat capacity of solid, C_{ps}	1250	J/K/ m ³

Fig. 9 shows the variations of gas pressure and adsorbed gas concentration both at the P1 and P2 observation points of simulation domain. It can be seen from Fig.9 that gas transport behaviours in micropores (below 2 nm) and mesopores (between 2 nm and 50 nm) are different. In micropores, when gas is in subcritical state (6 MPa used in this section), gas pressure gradually increases and reaches equilibrium at P1 observation point. When gas is supercritical, gas pressure increases rapidly at early stage compared to subcritical gas. However, when gas pressure approaches to a value that makes gas transforms from subcritical to supercritical state, the increase in gas pressure slows down followed by a gradual rise to equilibrium. The gas pressure in the centre of the domain displays a similar trend. Compared to the evolution of gas pressure in micropores, the time for reaching equilibrium in mesopores is reduced significantly. It takes approximately 100 hours to reach equilibrium state in pores with size of 1 nm when the applied pressure at the boundary is 15 MPa, while pressure reaching to equilibrium in pores of 5 nm takes about 10 hours. This implies that the increases of pore size could lead to obvious growth in gas diffusivity, as shown in Fig. 10. For larger pores, the pressure difference between two detection points becomes smaller, in other words, coal matrix containing larger pores, the gas pressure distribution in the entire matrix is nearly uniform.

The gas adsorption process in different pore sizes is presented in the right column of Fig. 9. It can be observed that the pore size affects the gas adsorption process. The adsorbed gas concentration shows an initial rapid increase, particularly in larger pores. Larger pores require shorter time to reach equilibrium. It is worth mentioning that the applied gas at supercritical state takes shorter time period to reach equilibrium than that of at the subcritical state for sizes of pores. For example, when boundary pressure is 6 MPa, it takes approximately 30 hours to reach equilibrium. However, 20 hours are required at supercritical state to reaching equilibrium in 1nm pores. Interestingly, it can be found that reaching pressure equilibrium and adsorption equilibrium are not synchronous, although the same surface diffusion coefficient is used in the simulations. When pore size is smaller than 10 nm, gas adsorption occurs earlier than the pressure to reach equilibrium. This is because the surface diffusion coefficient for adsorbed gas transport is larger than the effective diffusion coefficient for bulk phase gas migration. With an increase in pore size, the effective diffusion coefficient increases and surpasses surface

diffusion, which leads to early equilibrium of gas pressure. It can be concluded that the gas transport behaviour is pore size dependent.

Fig. 9 Evolution of gas pressure (right) and adsorbed concentration (left) at both detection points of matrix with different pore sizes.

As mentioned above, bulk gas diffusion coefficient is controlled by pressure and pore size under isotherm conditions. From Fig. 10, it can be seen that the apparent diffusion coefficient for bulk gas varies with pressure and pore sizes. When pore size is smaller than 5 nm and gas is subcritical, the apparent coefficient decreases with pressure, reaching to a minimum at gas pressure of 8 MPa. After which gas transforms from subcritical to supercritical state, and the apparent coefficient starts to increase slightly with pressure up to 14 MPa, and remains steady when pressure exceeds 14 MPa. As shown in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, Knudsen diffusion and viscous flow decrease with pressure rise when gas is subcritical. This can be attributed to: (1) the decrease in mean molecule free size caused by pressure rise and (2) pore size is reduced by coverage of the adsorbed molecule on the pore surface. After gas become supercritical, the mean molecule free path will increase, leading to increases in Knudsen diffusion and viscous flow. This is why the apparent diffusion coefficient decreases with pressure

increase and then rebounds. In comparison to the changes in viscous flow and Knudsen diffusion shown in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, it can be found that when pore size is smaller and gas is subcritical, the evolution of apparent coefficient is similar to that of Knudsen diffusion, this is because Knudsen diffusion makes greater contribution to gas transport, as shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 10 The effective diffusion coefficient of bulk gas varies with pressure for different pore sizes.

With increase of pore size, the effective diffusion coefficient increases due to significant increases of both Knudsen diffusion and viscous flow. However, the varied trend of apparent diffusion coefficient for bulk gas is very similar to that of viscous flow with pressure, which implies that when pore sizes are larger and pressure is larger, the viscous flow is dominant and the role of Knudsen diffusion can be ignored, as shown in Fig. 13. For larger pore sizes, when gas is subcritical, the viscous flow increases firstly with pressure up to 4 MPa and then drops gradually with pressure. When pressure approximates the critical value (8 MPa) that makes gas transform from subcritical to supercritical state, there is a sharp drop before pressure reaching 8 MPa and sharp increase after 8 MPa, this can be attributed to changes of gas compressibility and gas viscosity near the critical state. After gas becomes supercritical, the viscous flow shows a gradual increase with pressure. Similar phenomenon is also displayed for apparent diffusion coefficient.

Fig. 11 Viscous flow varies with gas pressure for different pore sizes.

Fig. 12 Knudsen diffusivity varies with gas pressure for different pore sizes.

Fig. 13 Comparison of the contributions of different transport mechanisms to bulk gas transport for different pore sizes (V-viscous flow, K-Knudsen diffusion).

It is worth pointing out that gas transport in coal matrix can also disturb the temperature field given that adsorption of the gas occurs in the matrix. Similar trend of temperature evolution is observed in the simulations. Here the temperature changes at both detection points for the boundary pressure of 6 MPa are presented in Fig. 6. It shows the thermal dynamics of gas adsorption in coal matrices. It can be observed that the temperature at both detection points experiences an increase at the early stages because of the release of heat during adsorption. After reaching a maximum, the temperature starts to decrease due to the effect of boundary temperature. Increase of temperature at both detection points are different with a larger increase at point P2. With increasing pore sizes, the time required to reach the maximum value is reduced as a result of rapid increase in gas adsorption. Interestingly, the time for temperature to reach the maximum is less than that for adsorbed gas concentration reaching equilibrium, as shown in Fig. 9. For example, Temperatures reaching to the maximum in pores of 1 nm take about 3 and 10 hours at both monitoring points P1 and P2, respectively, while 30 hours is required for adsorbed gas

concentration reaching equilibrium. Compared to the time required for temperature drop to the boundary temperature, temperature recovery time is almost same as that for gas adsorption reaching equilibrium. This suggests that the temperature variations can be used as an indication to the gas adsorption process.

Fig. 14 Temperature evolution at both detection points during gas transport in coal matrix with boundary gas pressure of 6 MPa.

From simulation results, it can be concluded that the gas diffusion- adsorption process is complex, which can be affected by factors including pressure, pore size. Due to lower diffusivity of gas near critical state, when considering geological sequestration, the pressure and temperature that can make gas near critical state should be avoided. On the other hand, gas adsorption/desorption in coal matrix can cause swelling/shrinkage, narrowing or open the cleats and affecting evolution coal permeability during gas production or gas injection from or into a coalbed reservoir. The coal matrix is of great heterogeneity with multiscale pores and low permeability^{8,18}, Therefore, varied gas diffusion should be taken into account for accurate estimation of gas production or gas injectivity.

5 Conclusions

This work focuses on the development of a coupled thermo-hydro-mechanical model to investigate the dynamic non-isothermal adsorption/desorption-diffusion-deformation behaviour of gas in coal matrix. The adsorbed phase gas on the interface between solid and free gas is viewed as an independent phase. The bulk gas transport process is described based on Knudsen number-based flow regimes, and surface diffusion is considered as the transport mechanism for adsorbed gas. The effects of temperature on gas transport-adsorption behaviour and the stress dependency of the porosity and intrinsic permeability are also included. The validity of proposed model has been examined by comparing with published experimental data to show the capability of developed model to capture the characteristics of gas

transport behaviour in matrix. The model is applied to investigate the transport processes of a real gas in coal matrix of multiple pore sizes. Our future work will consider the thermal and mechanical impacts on gas transport processes. Major findings are summarized as follows:

- (1) The evolutions of gas pressure and adsorption concentration in different sizes of pores are different. Compared to evolution of gas pressure in smaller pores, the time to reach equilibrium in larger mesopores is reduced significantly due to the larger diffusivity. The gas pressure and adsorbed gas concentration distribution in the entire matrix is nearly uniform before reaching equilibrium when the pore size is larger.
- (2) Pressure equilibrium and adsorption equilibrium are not synchronous, and depends on the pore size, pressure and surface diffusion. Applied gas at supercritical state takes shorter time to reach equilibrium than that at subcritical state for all pore sizes considered in this study.
- (3) The diffusivity in bulk gas transport is influenced by pressure and pore size. When pore size is smaller, and the gas is subcritical, the apparent diffusion coefficient drops with pressure. However, in larger pores, when gas is subcritical, the apparent diffusion coefficient increases firstly with pressure and then drops gradually with pressure. Gas transforming from subcritical to supercritical state leads to a sharp drop and a sharp increase before and after critical state. After gas becomes supercritical, the apparent diffusion coefficient shows an increase with pressure.
- (4) The apparent diffusion coefficient increases significantly with pore sizes. Knudsen diffusion is significant in bulk gas transport when the gas pressure is lower in smaller pores. However, when the pore size and the pressure are larger, the viscous flow plays dominant role in gas transport in the coal matrix.

Appendix

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Nomenclature

b	Slip coefficient
$B_{L\infty}$	Affinity at infinite temperature
C	Concentration of the free phase gas
C_{L0}	Maximum adsorption capacity of gas at a reference temperature T_0
C_{pa}	Specific heat capacity of adsorbed gas

C_{pg}	Specific heat capacity of free gas
C_{pg0}	Specific heat capacity for an ideal gas
C_{ps}	Specific heat capacity of solid skeleton
C_s	Adsorbed phase concentration
DC_{pg}	Departure function of specific heat capacity
d_f	Fractal dimension of the pore surface
d_m	Molecular diameter of gas adsorbed on the pore wall
D_K	Knudsen diffusion coefficient
D_s	Surface diffusion coefficient
D_s^0	Surface diffusivity at zero coverage
E	Adsorption heat
F_i	Component of the body force vector
J_f	Total flux of gas in bulk phase
J_{fv}	Gas flux from viscous flow
J_{fK}	Gas flux from Knudsen diffusion
J_s	Surface diffusion flux
K	Bulk modulus of matrix
K_s	Bulk modulus of the solid constituent
k	Permeability of coal matrix
k_0	Permeability under the effective stress σ_0 at reference state
k_∞	Intrinsic permeability of porous media
L	Volumetric strain coefficient of the gas
m	A material constant named the porosity sensitivity exponent
M	Gas molar weight
n_e	Effective porosity
n_0	Porosity at reference stress state
p	Pore fluid pressure
r_e	Effective pore radius
R	Universal gas constant
R_a, R_d	Rates of adsorption and desorption
r_h	Hydraulic radius
r_{ad}	Equivalent radius occupied by the adsorbed gas molecules
S	Sink/source term
S_h	Heat source term
T	Temperature
T_0	Reference temperature
Z	Gas compressibility factor
α	Biot coefficient
α_T	Thermal expansion coefficient
α'	Rarefaction coefficient
ε_{ad}	Adsorption-induced swelling strain
ε_{ij}	Component of the total strain tensor
ε_{ij}^e	Component of the elastic strain tensor
ε_T	Thermal expansion-induced volumetric strain
ε_v^e	Elastic volumetric strain
σ'_{ij}	Component of the effective stress tensor
σ_{ij}	Component of the total stress tensor
δ_{ij}	Kronecker's delta tensor
ν	Poisson's ratio
λ	Lamé constant
γ	Stress sensitivity coefficient
ω_ν, ω_K	Weighting coefficients

θ	Gas coverage on wall of micropores
μ	Gas viscosity
τ	Tortuosity
τ_r	A reduction coefficient related with temperature increase
ρ_g	Density of free gas
ρ_s	Density of solid skeleton
ρ_a	Density of adsorbed gas
λ_a	Thermal conductivity of adsorbed gas
λ_e	Effective thermal conductivity of media
γ_a, γ_d	Rate constant for adsorption and desorption
$\gamma_{d\infty}$	Rate constant of desorption at infinite temperature

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